

Mapping Black Heritage in Wellington County: An Exploration of Narrative, Settlement, and Space

How can I use a map to represent an affective experience of a community? Of Black settling, survival, and endurance? Particularly, how can a *map* capture these absent experiences when it originates from violent imperial processes of organising and delegating space as a method of domination and control? How can I map place onto the geographic space of a settlement?

My project focuses on mapping and narrativizing the history of the Queen's Bush Settlement in the form of a WebMap and StoryMap using ArcGIS. The settlement took place roughly from 1830-1859 in Waterloo and Wellington County, Ontario, and was one of the largest Black settlements with over 1,500 free and formerly enslaved Black people. I am currently partnering with the Guelph Black Heritage Society to develop the projects into my doctorate.

I knew where the Queen's Bush settlement was geographically, and used the information from Linda Brown-Kubisch's book *The Queen's Bush Settlement: Black Pioneers, 1839-1865* as well as the 1845 Peel Land Application document to get the lot and concession information. I used this information to plot the Black individuals, families, households, and significant buildings (school, church, mill, etc.) onto a base-map. I was able to get a sense of walking routes, mobility, and the overall largeness of the space that the settlement took up. What I was trying to glean into was the *place* and *community* of the settlement, and the Brown-Kubisch book offered glimpses of this, while the land document focused on the male experiences of applying for land and ownership. The land document, base-maps, and sources from the Brown-Kubisch text were coming out of imperial processes of land control, organisation, and transacting as a means of domination. When the texts are coming out of these conditions, how do I get to the affective experience that takes place at the core of these texts?

To get to the community of Queen's Bush, I used a method of "critical fabulation" (Hartman 11) which attempts to retrieve "a history of an unrecoverable past; it is a narrative of what might have been or could have been" (Hartman 12). I intently read through the two sources that featured male-dominated narratives of survival to engage with the conditions of fear and anxiety that the land document indicates was present, as well as the female-centred narratives of home-making and community building. The StoryMap combined both narrativized history and affectual experience, alongside a map of the geographic space, to provide a spatial exploration of space, place, and narrative.

I am currently further developing the WebMap in partnership with Guelph Black Heritage Society (GBHS) to include treaties, current city designations, and land values. This geographic space of Southwestern Ontario is invested with narratives of whiteness, maleness, and settlement in traditional colonial terms of "pioneering". I am combating these notions by using ArcGIS to knot a deeply intimate narrative of Black community with Indigenous histories, treaties, and current presence. My project is a public-facing digital tool that is deeply invested in providing access to materials about Black heritage that are largely inaccessible and absent from larger national narratives. My project meets a community interest in Black heritage and provides access to materials that are informative and interactive. The project shows how maps can be used as a transformative tool to fold Black heritage in with the complex history of the area and assert the prominence of Black presence into the history of Wellington County, Ontario.

Works Cited

Hartman, Saidiya. "Venus in Two Acts." *Small Axe*, vol. 12 no. 2, 2008, p. 1-14. Project MUSE muse.jhu.edu/article/241115.